

SQANTI3 report

Unique Genes: 14264

Unique Isoforms: 30611

Gene Classification

Category	Genes, count
Annotated Genes	13280
Novel Genes	984

Transcript Classification

Category	Isoforms, count
FSM	25103
ISM	0
NIC	1932
NNC	2037
Genic Genomic	147
Antisense	611
Fusion	244
Intergenic	488
Genic Intron	49

Splice Junction Classification

Category	SJs, count	Percent
Known canonical	130703	96.30
Known Non-canonical	163	0.12
Novel canonical	4816	3.55
Novel Non-canonical	40	0.03

Gene Characterization

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Known vs Novel Genes

Distribution of Mono- vs Multi-Exon Transcripts

All Transcript Lengths Distribution

Transcript Lengths Distribution by Structural Category

- FSM
- NNC
- Antisense
- Intergenic
- NIC
- Genic Genomic
- Fusion
- Genic Intron

Mono- vs Multi- Exon Transcript Lengths Distribution

Structural Isoform Characterization

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across FSM

Isoform Distribution Across NNC

Isoform Distribution Across NIC

Isoform Distribution Across Genic Genomic

Isoform Distribution Across Antisense

Isoform Distribution Across Fusion

Isoform Distribution Across Intergenic

Isoform Distribution Across Genic Intron

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Structural Classification

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Subcategories

Exon Count Distribution of Matched Reference Transcripts

Applicable Only to FSM and ISM Categories

Splice Junction Characterization

Distribution of Splice Junctions by Structural Classification

Distribution of Transcripts by Splice Junctions

RT-Switching All Junctions

Unique Junctions RT-switching

Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

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Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

*Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS
by Subcategories*

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

PolyA Distance Analysis

Frequency of PolyA Motifs

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Category	Count	polyA Detected	%
FSM	25103	18297	73
NIC	1932	1454	75
NNC	2037	1308	64
Genic Genomic	147	88	60
Antisense	611	281	46
Fusion	244	159	65
Intergenic	488	196	40
Genic Intron	49	22	45

Motif	Count	%
AATAAA	14648	67.2
ATTAAA	3414	15.7
AGTAAA	703	3.2
TATAAA	544	2.5
TTTAAA	313	1.4
CATAAA	309	1.4
AATATA	303	1.4
AATACA	274	1.3
AAGAAA	233	1.1
GATAAA	229	1.1
AAAAAG	211	1.0
AATGAA	189	0.9
AAAACA	125	0.6
ACTAAA	121	0.6
AATAGA	112	0.5
GGGGCT	77	0.4

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3'End by FSM and ISM Subcategories

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3'End by Non-FSM/ISM Subcategories

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Subcategory	Count	polyA Detected	%
Reference match	24392	17813	73
Comb. of annot. junctions	1101	841	76
Comb. of annot. splice sites	576	418	73
Intron retention	414	322	78
At least 1 annot. don./accept.	1899	1198	63
Mono-exon	711	484	68
Multi-exon	1518	729	48

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Redundancy Analysis

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Reference Transcript Redundancy

ISM per reference transcript

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only FSM with a polyA motif found

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only ISM with a polyA motif found

ISM per reference transcript

Reference Transcript Redundancy

FSM+ISM with a polyA motif found

Intra-Priming Quality Check

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

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Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Mono- vs Multi-Exon Possible Intra-Priming

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Coding vs Non-Coding Possible Intra-Priming

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Features of Bad Quality

RT-switching

Non-Canonical Junctions

Features of Good Quality

Annotation Support

PolyA Support

All Canonical Junctions

Good Quality Control Attributes Across Structural Categories

